

Use of titanium dioxide as photocatalyst for photodegradation of sodium lauryl sulfate

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The photocatalytic degradation of sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) over TiO_2 has been carried out. The effects of various parameters such as pH, variation of pH with time, concentration of surfactant, amount of semiconductor, effect of particle size, light intensity, etc. have been observed and a tentative mechanism has been proposed.

The extensive use of surfactants has created a new problem in environmental pollution, because surfactants are either slowly biodegraded or these do not biodegrade at all. The cationic surfactants undergo much slow biodegradation due to their bactericidal nature and are relatively more toxic as compared with other surfactants as far as plants and animals are concerned¹. So the surfactants are going to add a new feather in the cap of environmental pollution. It is, therefore, necessary to search for an alternate and quicker method for the treatment of used surfactant. This pressing demand results in the origin of the present investigation

Many surfactants that are widely used in various applications can cause severe problems for the natural aquatic environment². Biodegradation of surfactant is a very slow process and it is also inefficient³. Some studies on photocatalytic degradation of cationic surfactants have been reported by Hidaka *et al*^{4,5}. Swisher³ also reported that biodegradation of sodium *n*-dodecylbenzene sulfonate (DBS) requires a period of two days while branched isomers of DBS are not biodegraded even after a week of exposure to bacteria. Heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of the cationic surfactant dodecylpyridinium chloride has been observed by Avranas *et al*⁶. Recently, photocatalytic degradation of cetylpyridinium chloride over titanium dioxide has been reported by Singhal *et al*⁷. The present work describes the photocatalytic degradation of sodium lauryl sulfate over titanium dioxide. This detergent finds wide consumer and industrial use.

Results and Discussion

The plot of log (OD) vs exposure time is straight-line, which indicates that the photocatalytic degradation of sodium lauryl sulfate follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The rate constants (*k*) for the reaction were determined using the expression, $k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$.

Effect of pH : The photodegradation of sodium lauryl sulfate was investigated at different pH values. The results are given in Table 1. The maximum rate was observed when

Table 1. Effect of pH

[Sodium lauryl sulfate] = 6.93×10^{-5} M, TiO_2 = 0.30 g, Intensity = 65.0 mW cm^{-2} , Temp = 303 K

pH	$k \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$
2.0	2.55
3.0	4.49
4.0	6.08
5.0	7.11
6.0	8.01
7.0	8.63
8.0	7.42
9.0	4.35
10.0	1.03

the medium was neutral. Both in alkaline and in acidic medium, the rate of photodegradation was found to decrease. It may be explained on the basis that the titanium dioxide surface possesses charged O^- groups in alkaline medium. This negatively charged surface of TiO_2 particles will cause repulsion of the negatively charged (anionic) surfactant entity. This will retard the approach of lauryl sulfate ion towards TiO_2 surface to undergo photocatalytic degradation, thus causing the corresponding decrease in the rate of photodegradation. On the other hand, the surface of titanium dioxide will be positively charged in the acidic medium, because it possesses $^+\text{OH}_2$ groups on its surface. This positively charged surface will have a strong adsorption of lauryl sulfate anion due to columbic interaction. The attack of more reactive ^+OH radicals (formed via electron-hole pair) is thus checked and lowered. This will cause the corresponding decrease in the reaction rate.

Effect of variation of pH with time : The pH value of the reaction mixture was also measured at different time intervals during exposure with solutions, having different initial pH values. The results are presented in Fig. 1. It was observed that the pH of the reaction mixture changes on exposure and it almost approaches pH 8.5 for solution in

the pH range 7.0–10.0. However, the solution in the pH range 4.0–6.0 showed a similar behaviour but it increased to 6.1–8.1. On the contrary, for strongly acid solution with a lower pH values (pH 2.0–3.0), pH increases slightly thus indicating that the anionic surfactant sodium lauryl sulfate is photodegraded to a limited extent only in this range. Hidaka *et al.*⁵ observed that TiO₂ has an isoelectric point at pH 5.3. It was observed that the pH of an anionic surfactant solution (DBS) in the presence of TiO₂ approaches this point in most of the alkaline and neutral solutions but not in acidic solutions. The present observation is not in conformity with this observation, rather the curves pH vs time approach pH 8.5 in the present case.

Effect of the surfactant concentration : The effect of concentration of the anionic surfactant sodium lauryl sulfate on the rate of its photocatalytic degradation was also analyzed by taking solutions of different initial concentrations, keeping all other factors identical. The results are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of concentration of surfactant
TiO₂ = 0.30 g, Temp = 303 K, pH = 7.0, Light intensity = 65.0 mW cm⁻²

Sodium lauryl sulfate × 10 ⁵ M	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁵ s ⁻¹
1.73	6.21
3.46	7.67
5.20	8.24
6.93	8.63
8.66	8.30
10.40	7.60
12.13	7.28
13.87	6.12
15.60	5.56
17.33	4.26

It was observed that as the concentration of sodium lauryl sulfate is increased above 6.93×10^{-5} M, the rate of the reaction is decreased. At higher concentrations, the decomposition of sodium lauryl sulfate was so slow that no change in the concentration of the unreacted sodium lauryl sulfate was observed. It was virtually constant even after about 4 h of irradiation for solutions having concentrations above the critical micelle concentration (CMC), i.e. 8.6×10^{-3} M. It suggests that photodegradation of the anionic surfactant sodium lauryl sulphate can be carried out in solutions having concentrations below its CMC value. In other words, sodium lauryl sulfate can not be photodegraded easily, the moment it acquires a micellar structure.

The maximum rate was obtained at a concentration [SLS]

$= 6.93 \times 10^{-5}$ M. The decrease in the rate of the reaction with increase in the concentration of surfactant is due to the fact that higher concentrations will hinder the approach of surfactant towards TiO₂ surface. The micelle of sodium lauryl sulfate will have a negative surface potential, which is more dense as compared to a surfactant molecule. This will restrict the approach of this micelle on the TiO₂ surface, and hence there is no reaction even on a long term exposure. It is, therefore, necessary to keep the concentration of surfactant much below its CMC for its efficient photocatalytic degradation.

Effect of the amount of semiconductor : Keeping all other factors identical, the effect of amount of the titanium dioxide (photocatalyst) on the reaction rate has also been studied. It was observed that the rate of the reaction increases as the amount of semiconductor is increased. After a certain amount of semiconductor (0.30 g), the rate of photocatalytic degradation become constant. Any further increase in the amount showed no increase in the rate of the reaction. This observation may be explained on the basis that in the initial stage, even a small addition of semiconductor will increase the rate of reaction as the surface area of semiconductor increases, but after a certain amount of (0.30 g), addition of semiconductor does not effect the rate of reaction because of the fact that at this limiting amount, the surface at the bottom of the reaction vessel is completely covered with semiconductor. Now any further increase in the amount of semiconductor will only increase the thickness of the layer of semiconductor already formed at the bottom of the vessel and not the surface area.

Therefore, it may be concluded that the limiting value will depend on the geometry of the reaction vessel. This was confirmed in experiments, where reaction vessels of different dimensions were used. It was observed that this limiting value shifted to a higher range for larger vessels, whereas decrease in limiting value was observed for smaller vessels. Hence, the rate of photodegradation of the surfactant will remain unaffected by the addition of semiconductor above a certain range.

Effect of particle size : The effect of particle size on the rate of the reaction was also investigated by taking semiconductor particles of different sizes. Particle size of titanium dioxide was kept between 0.8–4.0 μm, and it was found that the rate of the reaction increases with a decrease in the particle size of semiconductor. This increase in rate may be explained on the basis of the increased surface area of the photocatalyst as the particle size was reduced.

Effect of light intensity : It was observed that increase in light intensity increases the rate of the reaction, as with

an increase in the light intensity, the number of photons striking per unit area of the semiconductor powder also increases. A linear behaviour between light intensity and rate of the reaction was observed.

Effect of sensitizers : The effect of sensitizers on the rate of the reaction was investigated and results are given in Table 3. It has been observed that sensitized TiO₂ photocatalyst is more efficient than unsensitized one. This may be attributed to the fact that sensitizer molecules absorb the light radiation of higher wavelength and transfer its energy to the semiconductor particle, thus making it a more active photocatalyst. All the five sensitizers were effective in increasing the photocatalytic activity of semiconductor titanium dioxide and the order of their efficiency is K₄Fe(CN)₆ > congo red > pyronine B > brilliant blue R > methylene blue > unsensitized. This trend can be correlated to their λ_{max} as it has been observed that with the decrease of λ_{max} the rate of photodegradation increases. This is due to the fact that a sensitizer with lower λ_{max} will absorb radiations of higher energy.

Table 3. Effect of sensitizer

[Sodium lauryl sulfate] = 6.93 × 10⁻⁵ M, TiO₂ = 0.30 g, pH = 7.0, Light intensity = 65.0 mW cm⁻²

Sensitizer	λ _{max} nm	k × 10 ⁵ s ⁻¹
	-	8.63
Methylene blue	661	9.04
Brilliant blue R	585	9.42
Pyronine B	533	13.21
Congo red	497	15.67
Potassium ferrocyanide	422	22.39

Mechanism : On the basis of the experimental observation, the following tentative mechanism has been proposed for the photocatalytic degradation of sodium lauryl sulfate.

The presence of water and oxygen is essential along with photocatalyst and light for rapid photocatalytic degradation of sodium lauryl sulfate. This was confirmed by control experiments carried out in non-aqueous medium and in inert atmosphere, respectively. Carbon dioxide was detected as

Fig. 1 Variation of pH with time

one of the products of photodegradation of sodium lauryl sulphate by its usual test with barium hydroxide. The participation of $\cdot OH$ radicals as the reactive oxidizing species was also confirmed by observing the rate of photocatalytic degradation of sodium lauryl sulfate in presence of an $\cdot OH$ radical scavenger, isopropanol, where the rate of reaction dropped almost to zero.

Experimental

The stock solution of sodium lauryl sulfate (0.05 g) was prepared in double-distilled water (1 dm³). To this solution (100 ml) titanium dioxide (0.30 g) was added and irradiated with a 1000 W halogen lamp (Okano, Japan; light intensity = 65.0 mW cm⁻²). The intensity of light at various distances from the lamp was measured with the help of a Surya Mapi CEL 201 solarimeter. A water-filter was used to cut out thermal radiations. The pH of the solution was measured by a pH meter (Systronics 324). The desired pH of the solution was adjusted by the addition of previously standardized sulfuric acid and sodium hydroxide solution. The necessary condition for the correct measurement of the optical density is that the solution must be free from semiconductor particles and impurity; a centrifuge (REMI 1258) was used to remove these species. The changes in the concentrations of the anionic surfactants were determined by the methylene blue active substance (MBAS) method. The

photodegraded solution (1.5 ml) of the anionic surfactant (where TiO₂ particles were removed by centrifugation and further filtration) was added to an aqueous solution containing 0.25% methylene blue (5 ml) and 4% alkaline sodium tetraborate (10 ml). The active substance was then extracted with chloroform (10 ml). The absorbance of this solution was then determined with a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV 160) at 650 nm. This provided the amount of unreacted sodium lauryl sulfate.

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